

COMPARISON OF SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AMONG STUDENT POLICE CADETS AND NON-STUDENT POLICE CADETS

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***Abstract:** The present investigation is an attempt to study the Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadets and Non-Student Police Cadets with special reference to gender. For this the investigator used Normative Survey Method. Sample for the present study include 300 Ninth standard students from Aided schools of Kottayam District of Kerala State. The data pertaining to the objectives are collected by administering the tool titled Social Responsibility Scale constructed by the investigator. The investigator administered the tool on 150 Student Police Cadets and 150 Non-Student Police Cadets of Standard Nine, each category consists of 75 boys and 75 girls. For the analysis of data, the investigator used statistical technique, Test of Significance of the difference between Means. The findings of the present study revealed that Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadets is higher than that of Non-Student Police Cadets irrespective of gender. Hence the Student Police Cadet Programme can be widely implemented in schools to promote Social Responsibility.*

(Key Words; Social Responsibility, Student Police Cadets, Non-Student Police Cadets, Student Police Cadet Boys, Student Police Cadet Girls, Non-Student Police Cadet Boys, Non-Student Police Cadet Girls)

Introduction

Education is one of the most powerful systems in a nation contributing for its growth and development. The education system of the society reflects its culture and development, and for the development of the nation, there has to be an increase in its democratic participation. This participation will in turn enhance nation building initiative as citizen participation counts a lot in nation building. Citizen participation can be ensured if it starts with students. It is important for students to understand their inevitable role in the community. In schools many programmes like NSS, NCC, Scout and Guide, Red Cross and Student Police Cadet Programme are started for developing social qualities and make them efficient human beings.

Student Police Cadet Programme of the Government of Kerala which seeks to mould responsible youth for creating vigilant, peaceful, value-based society, for whom disciplined adherence to law is a way of life. Student Police Cadets are those students who are active members of Student Police Cadet Project in the secondary school. It trains high school students to evolve as future leaders of a democratic society by inculcating within them respect for the law, discipline, civic sense, empathy for vulnerable sections of society and resistance to social evils. The

project also enables youth to explore and develop their innate capabilities, there by empowering them to resist the growth of negative tendencies.

The present study is to compare Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadets and Non-Student Police Cadets with special reference to gender.

Need and Significance of the Study

In modern times we are facing a drastic value crisis throughout the world. Weakening of moral and social values in our society is creating serious social and ethical problems around the globe. The world has become more and more complex. Inter personal relationship are the heart and soul of human experience. Education is a never-ending quest for the best and a transformation from the crude and chaotic to the refined and disciplined which is fundamental requisite for moulding the character of a person. It has a major role in promoting values required for co-operative living.

Social Responsibility is an essential quality of socially efficient individuals. Individuals are unique so there is a need to promote qualities which are necessary in the society. So Self Discipline is the best quality that makes some discipline in the behaviour of the students. Schools can promote Social Responsibility through various programmes. So, Student Police Cadet Programme is an important programme intended to develop these qualities. By introducing the project in school level, the Government wants to develop Social Responsibility among the cadets so that they will become more conscious about the democratic values and their role in nation building.

It is important to evaluate the relevance of Student Police Cadet Project in developing Social Responsibility. It is also important to find out the Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Girls. It is essential to investigate whether the programme attains its goal or it is needed to have some modification in order to attain its goal. The study is significant for teachers, school authorities, parents, curriculum designers, society and coordinators of Student Police Cadet Project. Because based on the study they can choose appropriate steps that contribute to the all-round development of the students.

Objectives of the Study

The major objectives of the present study are the following;

1. To compare the Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Student Police Cadet Girls
2. To compare the Social Responsibility compare among Student Police Cadet Boys and Non-Student Police Cadet Boys.
3. To compare the Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Girls and Non-Student Police Cadet Girls.

Methodology

The present investigation is an attempt to study Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadets and Non-Student Police Cadets belonging to both gender groups. For this the investigator used Normative Survey Method. Sample for the study include 300 Ninth standard students from Aided schools (150 Student Police Cadets and 150 Non-Student Police Cadets) of Kottayam District of Kerala State. The data pertaining to the objectives are collected by administering the tool titled Social Responsibility Scale constructed by the investigator. The investigator administered the tool on 150 Student Police Cadets and 150 Non-Student Police Cadets of Standard Nine. Each group consists of 75 boys and 75 girls. For the analysis of data, the investigator used appropriate statistical technique namely Test of Significance of the difference between Means.

Analysis and Interpretation

Comparison of Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Student Police Cadet Girls

To study the significant difference if any between the Means of Scores on Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Student Police Cadet Girls, the investigator used two tailed t-test for large independent sample. The t-value was set as 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with degree of freedom 148(n=150). The result is presented in the table 1.

Table 1.

Number, Mean, Standard Deviation and t-value of the score on Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Student Police Cadet Girls

Variable	Category	No.	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	Remarks
Social Responsibility	S.P.C boys	75	88.68	5.35	148	0.74	Not Significant at 0.01 level
	S.P.C girls	75	89.33	5.52			

From the table, the investigator observes that the obtained t-value 0.74 is less than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence it may be said that there is no significant difference between the Means of Scores of Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Student Police Cadet Girls. The Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Student Police Cadet Girls is almost same.

Comparison of Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Non-Student Police Cadet Boys.

To study the significant difference if any between the Means of Scores on Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and non-Student Police Cadet Boys, the investigator used two tailed t-test for large independent sample. The t-value was set as 2.58 at 0.01 level of significance and with degree of freedom 148(n=150). The result is presented in the table 2.

Table 2.

Number, Mean, Standard Deviation and t-value of the score on Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Non-Student Police Cadet Boys.

Variable	Category	No.	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	Remarks
Social Responsibility	S.P.C Boys	75	88.68	5.35	148	7.034	Significant at 0.01 level
	Non S.P.C Boys	75	81.62	6.84			

From the table, the investigator observes that the obtained t-value 7.04 is greater than the table value 2.58 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence it may be said that there is significant difference between the Means of Scores on Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Non-Student Police Cadet Boys. The Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadets Boys is greater than that of Non-Student Police Cadet Boys.

Comparison of Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Girls and Non-Student Police Cadet Girls

To study the significant difference if any between the Means of Scores on Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Girls and Non-Student Police Cadet Girls, the investigator used two tailed t-test for large independent sample. The t-value was set as 2.58 at 0.01 level of significance and with degree of freedom 148(n=150). The result is presented in the table 3.

Table 3

Number, Mean, Standard Deviation and t-value of the score on Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Girls and Non-Student Police Cadet Girls

Variable	Category	No.	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	Remarks
Social Responsibility	S.P.C Girls	75	89.33	5.52	148	3.03	Significant at 0.01level
	Non S.P.C Girls	75	86.12	7.34			

From the table the investigator observes that the obtained t-value 3.03 is greater than the table value 2.58 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence it may be said that there is significant difference between the Means of Scores of Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Girls and Non-Student Police Cadet Girls. The Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadets Girls is greater than that of Non-Student Police Cadet Girls.

Major Findings of the Study

1. There is no significant difference between the means of scores of Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Student Police Cadet Girls. The Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Student Police Cadet Girls is almost same.

2. There is significant difference between the means of scores of Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Non-Student Police Cadet Boys. The Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadets Boys is greater than that of Non-Student Police Cadet Boys.

3. There is significant difference between the means of scores of Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Girls and Non-Student Police Cadet Girls. The Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadets Girls is greater than that of Non-Student Police Cadet Girls.

Conclusion

Social Responsibility is an important quality that is to be developed among students. Schools can play an important role in this regard. Student Police Cadet Programme in schools can promote social values like Social Responsibility among students. The findings of the present study revealed that Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadets is higher than that of Non-Student Police Cadets irrespective of gender. Self-Discipline Social Responsibility among Student Police Cadet Boys and Student Police Cadet Girls is higher than that of Non-Student Police Cadets Boys and Girls. Hence the Student Police Cadet Programme can be widely implemented in schools to promote Social Responsibility.

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